

EXPLORING SPEAKING DIFFICULTIES ENCOUNTERED BY ENGLISH MAJOR STUDENTS: A CASE STUDY

¹LYN B. AYOP, ²SHERYL LAINE C. NAMOCOT, PhD

Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges

Graduate School

General Santos City, Philippines

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Abstract: The purpose of this qualitative study was to describe the cases of the seven Bachelor of Secondary Education, majors in English students at GenSantos Foundation College, Incorporated concerning their English-speaking difficulties and the coping mechanisms they have employed to address their problems. Using a case study method, there were six essential themes found in describing the English-speaking difficulties encountered by the English major students, these themes were: lack of speaking practice, lack of word usage, fear of mistakes, unfamiliar words pronunciation, low motivation, and lack of general knowledge. On the other hand, eight essential themes were found in the coping mechanisms of the English major students, specifically, being ready, accepting feedback, practicing English, reading books, watching English movies, building self-confidence, seeking help, and taking notes. Furthermore, the study's key results may be able to help the school in designing a springboard to address the concern of the English major students concerning their experiences with speaking difficulties. Lastly, this study may help future researchers to learn and understand important information about the speaking difficulties of English major students and the effective strategies to cope with them; they may also use this study as a basis whenever they wanted to conduct related research about exploring speaking difficulties of English major students.

Keywords: English speaking difficulties, English major students, case study, Philippines.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the international arena, one of those languages with a demand for learners from a variety of backgrounds at all levels of communication is English. However, the increasing speaking abilities of English-major students are consistently viewed as sophisticated and complex, requiring much work to sustain. Only some people are capable of speaking effectively and sensibly with prior instruction. As a result, English language teachers should assist pupils with the most exceptional abilities in achieving this speaking objective (Aziz & Kashinathan, 2021; Al-Abri, 2018; Khatoony & Rahmani, 2020).

More specifically, in the Philippine context, there has been consistent and systematic documentation of students' speaking difficulties associated with using English as the medium of instruction. Such reports were noted very early in implementing the English language policy. The study by Leño et al. (2019) revealed that speaking activity, error correction, and communicating with English speakers are sources of high anxiety among Filipino English learners (Amoah & Yeboah, 2021; Ekoc, 2020; Ulla, 2018).

Based on the researcher's pre-gathered data on the student's performance in English, the English Education Department of GenSantos Foundation College, Incorporated, 55% of the students have encountered difficulties when speaking English. Experienced. English teachers and students need help with speaking English, such as mispronouncing English words, lack of self-confidence, lack of vocabulary, and fear of making mistakes, which hinder their speaking. Also, some students understand the English language very well but then feel more comfortable when they have to speak English. They spoke with a lower voice and looked very nervous. In addition, they need more confidence to speak naturally, and they are in doubt about expressing their sentences in English. That is why they need to speak up in the classroom. If the students make any mistakes, the teacher can help correct them.

The gaps presented in the preceding paragraphs served as a motivating ground to conduct a study to explore the speaking difficulties encountered by English primary students at Gensantos Foundation College, Incorporated. Also, this research wanted to know how speaking difficulties among English-major students could be described and their coping mechanisms to address their speaking difficulties. The solutions found from the study could help English students deal with their speaking problems. This study could impact many people, whether the students, the English teachers, or future researchers.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this undertaking was to describe the speaking difficulties encountered by the seven (7) third-year Bachelor Secondary of Education significant in English Students of Gensantos Foundation College, Incorporated (GFI), General Santos City. Likewise, it also unearthed their daily struggles as English Majors as they will soon be pre-service teachers in the field. With the need for their future learners to be proficient in utilizing the universal language, it is vital to know the present status of their skills in English. Finally, this single case study likewise discovered their coping mechanisms in handling English-speaking difficulties.

Research Question

This single case aimed to explore the speaking difficulties encountered by English-major students in GenSantos Foundation College, Incorporated. Specifically, this study addressed the following questions:

1. How do the students describe their difficulties in speaking English?
 - 1.1 How do speaking difficulties among the participants be viewed?
 - 1.2 How do speaking difficulties being coped by the participants?

Theoretical Lens

This qualitative research was rooted in the Speech Act theory of J.L. Austin (1975), supported by the study of Nunan (1999) on Second Language Teaching and Learning, Cognition on lexical access in speech production by W.J.M Levelt (1989); and Robinson's Triadic Componential Framework (Robinson, 2007).

Several theories regarding speaking ability and verbal skills indicate learners' capacity to produce language. One of the most preliminary theories in this term is on 'speech acts' in speaking. In this theory, the Speech act is the speaker's intention and influence on the listener, which contains answering, promising, and apologizing. According to Austin (1975), there are three types of speech acts, including locutionary, illocutionary, and perlocutionary; each is needed to be defined (Christison, 2018). The illocutionary speech acts, which are actions performed while speaking, locutionary speech acts are utterances focused on performance and involve the listener and the speaker. Finally, a perlocutionary act is a speech that affects the audience by impacting the listener. In other words, when there is a sentence, the speaker does an illocutionary act with a specific force instead of a locutionary act with a meaning and a perlocutionary act that aims to produce specific results.

Further, considering that one of the most important and challenging skills in teaching English is speaking skill, Nunan (1999), in his Second Language Teaching and Learning study, states that language can have two parts: monologue and dialogue. A monologue has only one speaker, while dialogue has more than one speaker. Based on the theory of behaviorism and the audio-lingual method, students need to make a habit formation of the target language. Finally, they should interact and communicate with the language they know, corresponding to 'communicative language teaching.' Based on Edge in Pendidikan (2012), language production (speaking) has the following abilities, including developing meanings logically,

expressing unambiguously the function of what one says or writes, and using language appropriate for the people one is addressing”.

Moreover, the Cognition on lexical access in speech production by Levelt (1989) emphasized the approaches to the speech production process. According to him, one approach is cognitive, where underlying psycholinguistics processes such as planning what to say, retrieving the necessary grammar and vocabulary, and articulating the words are highlighted (Bygate, 1998; Levelt, 1989). This psycholinguistic perspective suggests that the speech production processes of non-native speakers in some ways resemble, and in other ways are distinct, from those of native speakers. From this psycholinguistic perspective, if speech production needs to be smooth, the underlying processes must be automatic, which is a demanding task for most second or foreign-language learners. Drawing on Levelt's (1989) model of the speech production process, aspects of speech such as fluency, accuracy, and complexity compete for processing capacity due to the inherent limited attentional and reasoning resources humans can invest in solving a task.

Finally, Robinson's Triadic Componential Framework (Robinson, 2007) specifies that language learners can access multiple attentional pools that do not compete, and the depletion of attention in one pool does not affect the amount remaining in another. Language learners can prioritize different aspects of oral production, including accuracy and complexity.

2. METHOD

Research Design

This study utilized a single case study analysis under qualitative research. In this study, a single case study was designed to investigate the in-depth phenomena of English Major students to provide detailed descriptions and understanding of their experiences with speaking difficulties in English; also, a single case study focused on the events surrounding one case in a contemporary context or setting. This evaluation method, which frequently goes by the name single subject design and involves repeated measurements and the manipulation of an independent variable, can be used to rigorously test specific cases like a person, school, or community (Ledford & Gast, 2018; Riley-Tillman et al., 2020; Tincani & Travers, 2018).

Research Participants

This research described information about the 17 Bachelor of Secondary Education majors in English students' problems in speaking English and the coping mechanism they used to overcome their speaking difficulties. This study combined observation with an interview by verbally answering the prepared interview guide. In summary, the researcher focused on the essential structure of a single case study by interviewing several in-depth English major individuals who served as study participants who belonged in this category (Rashid et al., 2019).

Data Analysis Procedures

In conducting the study, followed were the steps such as researcher sent a research proposal to the office of the Research Ethics Committee for ethical review; once the RMMC-ERC sent their approval, an endorsement letter from Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges was immediately requested through the office of the Dean to conduct the study; then, sent was the letter to the validators for them to validate the interview guide questions, followed by a letter of invitation with the informed consent form to the informants. Second, the researcher explained to the participants the study's primary purpose and saw to it that their participation was voluntary; the participants were encouraged to be open in answering the form; I gave instructions on how to fill them out. A researcher emphasized the manner of recruitment free of coercion, undue influence, or inducement; after distributing the consent form to secure confidentiality personally. Third, an in-depth interview was conducted and ensured that students with a Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in English could express their ideas freely.

Trustworthiness

Further, this study followed the data analysis procedure recommended by Schoch (2020), which emphasized the basic phases of steps such as describing, interpreting, drawing conclusions, comparing, and reporting. To develop trustworthiness, this study followed the four components: credibility, conformability, transferability, and dependability (Korstjens & Moser, 2018; Stahl & King, 2020).

3. RESULTS

Table 1. The Thematic Analysis of the Description of the Participants' Difficulties in Speaking English

Essential Themes	Core Ideas
Lack of Speaking Practice	<p><i>The participants are...</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • unable to express themselves due to lack of speaking practice • hesitant to speak because of being afraid to be judged and they are not used to speaking English • unable to speak English in front of many people • confused about the grammar rules and afraid to speak with the wrong grammar • hesitant to speak due to their speaking skills
Lack of Word Usage	<p><i>The participants...</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • unable to find the appropriate words to use • feel embarrassed whenever they cannot speak English well • are not that knowledgeable about English word usage which is why they got embarrassed whenever they are being corrected by the teacher • experienced embarrassment in front of the crowd because of using English words incorrectly
Fear of Mistakes	<p><i>The participants are...</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • afraid to speak English • afraid to commit mistakes • scared whenever they cannot translate the mother tongue words into English • scared to experience being mental-block whenever they speak in front • nervous whenever they have an oral recitation
Unfamiliar Words Pronunciation	<p><i>The participants...</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • are unable to properly voice out because they cannot properly pronounce English words • are being laughed at because of mispronounced words • find it difficult to speak because they are not used to the English language • conclude that they have a poor vocabulary which also leads them to mispronounce words • shared that whenever they are unfamiliar with English words, they mispronounced them
Low Motivation	<p><i>The participants...</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • have low self-esteem whenever they speak English in front of a crowd because they are not that motivated to study English • are shy because they have a hard time speaking English • lose their confidence when they talk to someone fluent in English • are not motivated in delivering speeches • feel tense whenever they speak the English language
Lack of General Knowledge	<p><i>The participants...</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • considered their knowledge of English as average • can understand and speak English but they are not that fluent • have a background on how to speak the English language but still cannot speak fluently • have a lack of general knowledge of English which is why they have speaking difficulty problem

Lack of Speaking Practice

Lack of Speaking Practice is one of the participants' experiences of difficulty speaking English. P1, P3, P4, and P5 shared that they cannot express themselves due to a lack of practice in speaking English. Also, they are hesitant to speak because they fear being judged, especially in front of many people, need help finding the correct words, and need clarification about the grammar rules.

This result implies that these students must overcome these problems through regular practice. Repeated practice in speaking the English language is crucial. One can also read English books, watch English movies, and converse with someone fluent in English. Thus, the teachers of GFI may conduct regular speech sessions to give ample time for the English major students to rehearse.

Lack of Word Usage

The participants have experienced the embarrassment of having difficulties in speaking English because of a lack of word usage. They feel embarrassed whenever they cannot use the English words well and when the teacher corrects them. They are also shy when they speak incorrect English words in front of many people. The result implies that it is easier for students to read and pronounce a text if they need to learn what the words mean—a solid vocabulary and speech boost reading comprehension and pronunciation for students of all ages. The more words students know, the better they understand the text. The more correct words a student utters, the more correct word usage he applies. Practical vocabulary and speech teaching are important, especially for students who learn and think differently. Therefore, there is a need to give ample time for English learners to reflect on what they know, what they said, or what they do not know about the words being uttered.

Fear of Mistakes

The participants have a fear of committing mistakes whenever they speak the English language; they are afraid to speak and get scared whenever they cannot translate words into English. Psychology says that the fear of committing mistakes is a common reaction of students who always look at a standard. Making mistakes is a regular thing. No one is born perfect; everyone makes mistakes, but they should overcome their mistakes in speaking English. Fear of failure is also associated with using less effective learning strategies. These increased stress levels, loss of control, and loss of confidence all negatively impact student resilience (Kinkead, 2020). The most effective method for putting this into practice is to engage in conversation with a person who is familiar to you and with whom you feel at ease. If a person is with a friend who does not criticize the way that another person speaks English, then that person will not need to worry. It is critical to maintain a regular practice routine for one's English speaking skills.

Unfamiliar Word Pronunciation

Based on the participants' responses, most concluded that they struggle with unfamiliar word pronunciation. Those not used to speaking English are more likely to have difficulty acquiring intelligible pronunciation, with the difficulty increasing markedly. Thus, the participants said they could not properly voice out or express themselves freely because they could not correctly pronounce English words. Because of mispronounced words, being laughed at causes them to struggle. On the other hand, they also conclude that they need a better vocabulary, leading them to mispronounce words.

Vocabulary is key to speaking and reading comprehension. Speakers and readers need to know what most words mean to understand what they are saying and reading. As children progress through the levels of reading instruction, they are faced with the challenge of decoding new words that are not a part of their spoken vocabulary. It is recommended to employ word pieces (roots, prefixes, and suffixes) to identify the meaning of an unknown word. According to Lestari and Wahyudin's 2020 research, you can determine the meaning of an unfamiliar word by looking for hints in its context. In addition, it is recommended that you use a visual organizer to get a more in-depth grasp of specific vocabulary words if you want to improve your overall vocabulary skills.

Low Motivation

The participants feel they need more confidence whenever they speak English. They have low motivation; they feel demotivated every time they speak English in front of many people. Sometimes, they also feel shy and pressured when talking to someone fluent in speaking English. Additionally, when delivering speeches, they feel tense whenever they speak English.

Teaching English is quite challenging, especially in teaching speaking. Most English students find that they can understand their English teacher, but when they speak to native speakers or are called 'real people,' they cannot understand them. In effect, their motivation to speak tends to get lower. According to Putri et al. (2019), motivation is much needed in doing everything, including learning something. In learning a language, a learner needs motivation because it helps him or her in trying and developing his or her understanding of a new language. With motivation, a learner wants to succeed. So, without it, he or she will certainly fail to make the necessary effort. Hence, English teachers should find things that students need. They should know what kind of activities will work in class, which will help students to face real interaction.

Lack of General Knowledge

Some participants also concluded that they need more general knowledge of English. They concluded that they only have average English-speaking skills. Also, they need to be more fluent, and even though they can understand English, they can still not speak it fluently. The results of the English-major students' responses show negative and positive experiences of difficulties speaking English. It streams from different causes that make English students struggle when speaking English. The lack of general knowledge about speaking English can be treated by constantly learning varied concepts, practicing, and applying what has been learned. Thus, the teachers have to make environments where students can feel comfortable speaking English and asking questions. Learning the English language is the process of speaking the English language with other people and in public fluently. The teachers must focus on oral communication in English rather than learning from books and exercises. Through oral communication, students can quickly learn, communicate, and feel comfortable speaking with others.

Table 2. The Thematic Analysis of the Coping Mechanisms of Participants on Their Difficulties in Speaking English

Being Ready	<p><i>The participant...</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> prepares himself whenever there is a scheduled oral recitation confirms that being ready is very important so that he will not cram in the actual presentation
Accepting Feedbacks	<p><i>The participants...</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> are willing to accept positive criticism to become better English speakers listen to the feedback of their teachers and be eager to accept pieces of advice on how to use the English language apply what they have learned from the feedback given by the teachers find the teachers' feedback useful especially during reporting and they use the English language learn a lot from the feedback of their teachers and do their best not to repeat the same mistakes
Practicing English	<p><i>The participants...</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> practice the use of the English language whenever they talk with their friends and others use the English language when communicating ask questions to the teachers using the English language conclude that practicing helps them overcome their difficulties in speaking English practice in front of the mirror while speaking the English language
Reading Books	<p><i>The participants...</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> find English books helpful whenever they want to learn English words read the novels to widen their vocabulary make it a habit to read English books to become fluent consider reading as a coping mechanism to ease their problems in understanding English words
Watching English Movies	<p><i>The participants...</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> watch English movies with subtitles to learn some English words watch movies so that they can practice how to speak certain English words love to watch English movies to widen their knowledge about the English language
Building Self-Confidence	<p><i>The participants...</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> cope with their difficulties in speaking English by doing their best to build their self-confidence

Seeking Help

- read books, watch movies, and talk with people to build self-confidence
- try to speak in front of the crowd using the English language to conquer their fears and become confident in speaking

The participants...

- are not afraid to ask for help whenever they cannot understand the English words
- seek help from their teacher in learning the English language
- accept that seeking help is very important to cope with their difficulties in speaking English
- feel very happy whenever their teacher provides them with relevant materials to learn more about English
- ask teachers to help them improve their speaking skills

Taking Notes

The participant...

- values the importance of taking down some English words so that they cannot forget their meaning
- take note of the English words of some experts every time they have a conversation

Table 2 shows the English-major students’ coping mechanisms for their difficulties in speaking English. Presented are the essential themes and core ideas to describe the findings comprehensively.

Being Ready

The participant prepares himself whenever there is a scheduled oral recitation; he reaffirms that being prepared is of utmost significance so that he does not have to rush through the actual presentation. Being ready needs enough preparation. Preparation is giving the students ample time to prepare for oral tasks. This gives the students the leisure to compose their outline of what to say and how they deliver their message. According to Thorndike (1932), only when the students are ready to learn can learning happen or his Law of Readiness. It resonates with the notion that to be pressured to learn while not ready results in an unpleasant circumstance in learning. Thus, Thorndike’s view sparks motivation as a crucial component in the learning process. As a result, the coping strategies outlined above place a value on creating a language learning atmosphere that is welcoming, comfortable, and non-threatening to L2 students. It is displayed by providing adequate time for students to prepare, reflect, and speak, demonstrating a positive attitude from the teacher, such as teacher support or scaffolding, and fostering positive thinking through collaborative activities or assignments.

Accepting Feedback

Participants are very willing to accept their English teachers' Feedback. That Feedback is helpful for their growth in learning more about the English language. They found Feedback to help improve their English-speaking skills. They have learned that there is always room for improvement, and practice helps them improve. Across the data sets, constructive Feedback was the participants' preference in handling errors in speaking English. Undeniably, making mistakes or errors in grammar has brought them so much concern. Park (2010) asserted that the teacher and the student's perception of correcting errors often mismatched in the classroom setup, leading to severe language disappointments. That is why teachers' and students' expectations of handling errors should meet. Teachers' constructive Feedback was encouraged rather than interrupting and correcting the students directly, even without finishing their communication attempts (Hashemi, 2011).

The students see constructive Feedback as having a pivotal role in their development. That poorly done error correction and the strict attitude of the teachers would not aid the students in learning the second language at all. There is a need for constructive Feedback with proper timing, tone of voice, and content. In an English classroom, teachers' perception of error correction and students' expectations on how to treat their errors must meet halfway. This was emphasized by Martin et al. (2017), who concluded that teachers should reinforce Feedback to generate a positive feeling for the students.

Practicing English

Practicing English served as a great coping mechanism for the participants. They practice using English whenever they talk with their friends and others. English conversation is a great avenue for them to enhance their speaking skills. They conclude that practicing English help them overcome their difficulties in speaking English. Implementing a vocabulary practice strategy facilitates a learning climate to be rich and literate. Consulting and understanding the meaning of a newly accustomed word or term is a learning habit that increases vocabulary gain and word knowledge fundamentals in most

students. However, when students have a restricted vocabulary, it is difficult for them to put their thoughts into words, and it causes them to feel apprehensive when they have to speak English. Hence, there should be a rich provision of comprehensible input in the learning environment so that English learners can practice speaking (Schutz, 2019).

Reading Books

Reading books help the participants overcome their English language difficulties. It helps them to widen their vocabulary and learn the meaning of the words. Reading also allows them to explore and discover beautiful ideas. Also, listening to audiobooks help the participants in learning how to pronounce English words correctly. Reading English books for leisure and academic purposes was a strategy the participants used to cope with the phenomenon. They consistently admitted that in reading, they still got the chance to be accustomed to new vocabulary in English and be acquainted with how these terms were used in the sentences. They have encountered new ideas and points of view that they have used as references in their future classes. Indeed, reading English in printed and non-printed forms was a helpful activity used by the participants to minimize their perceived fear of the target language. Their self-directed reading was considered their independent learning, enabling them to choose any text based on their interest. As a result, this self-initiative has developed their motivation and enthusiasm since their learning preferences and interest was acknowledged.

Establishing their language proficiency through utilizing helpful tools like reading English books and dictionary use strategy, in return, reduced the amount of anxiety felt by the participants towards the English language. When confidence was established among them, they became more comfortable and at ease with English. Their confidence had made them more willing to practice speaking in any oral task, and they were trying to speak their thoughts instead of being silent, reserved, and unfriendly with the target language.

Watching English Movies

The participants agreed that watching movies in English was an extremely helpful activity for improving their pronunciation skills, and they recommended doing so whenever possible. Also, watching movies is another way to expand vocabulary. Similarly, Wilkins (1972, cited in Alhatmi, 2019) duly expressed, "Without grammar, very little can be conveyed; without vocabulary, nothing can be conveyed." That is why watching English movies strategy is a helpful task that has assisted the participants in becoming independent English speakers. This strategy was employed due to accessibility and convenience. This coping strategy is compelling enough for them to deal with their English language-speaking anxiety.

Building Self-Confidence

The participants cope with the difficulties in speaking English by building self-confidence by reading books, watching movies, talking with people using English, conquering their fears, and joining public speaking. Building self-confidence is always challenging for them, but through determination, they believe they can do it to become a great English speaker in the future.

The narrative above reveals that oral recitation, reporting, demonstration, and watching television can mitigate their shyness in speaking in front of others. Consequently, it improved their capacity to speak and thus enhanced their self-esteem. Establishing their language proficiency through helpful tools like reading English books and dictionary use strategy, in return, reduced the amount of anxiety felt by the participants towards the English language. When confidence was established among them, they became more comfortable and at ease with English. Their confidence had made them more willing to practice speaking in any oral task, and they were trying to speak their thoughts instead of being silent, reserved, and unfriendly with the target language.

Seeking Help

Participants 4,5 and 7 are open to asking for help whenever they need help understanding English words; they seek help from their teacher in learning the English language and are very willing to be corrected. Also, they feel pleased whenever their teacher provides relevant materials to learn more about English. The informants shared that when they are secure with their environment, this facilitates them to be composed and to go the extra mile in their language education. Promoting a learning climate to be non-threatening and friendly as part of the teacher's strategy fosters ease and a comfortable English learning environment. Hence, this learning condition facilitates a persuasive impact on ESL students to become more relaxed and secure. This is in conformance with Saltmarsh & McPherson's (2022) view that the "brain is shaped as it interacts with the environment...." When the learning climate is non-threatening and comfortable, students are less anxious. Students can maximize their full potential in a friendly environment because they become more willing to explore and participate.

Taking Notes

Participant 5 values the importance of taking down some English words so that he cannot forget them; in fact, Participant 5 also shared that taking notes help him to learn more about English words. Utilizing helpful tools has improved the participants' basic foundation in the target language, such as building one's word knowledge and understanding word meaning, sentence usage, and word pronunciation. Furthermore, this has facilitated their skills to put their thoughts into writing. The participants experienced great excitement to apply their new vocabulary in any writing task, particularly in composing an essay. Through this means, the chosen participants became capacitated to utilize their newfound words or terms to translate their messages into written discourse. Writing has also given them opportunities to recognize the ideas they have in their mind from what they have read. Through this, they have channeled and recognized their acquired information and ideas into written expression. This strategy helped them in coping with their anxiety.

English major students were more likely to familiarize themselves with the target language structure through their writing engagement. Their writing competence was aided by their reading, which is a valuable coping mechanism for acquiring proficiency in English. The more the students were exposed to reading, their writing skills were fostered and developed.

4. DISCUSSION

The Case of P1

P1 is a third-year, section 1 college student. He is 21 years old and can speak Tagalog, Cebuano, and English. He usually speaks Tagalog. Based on the results, he said that he needs more speaking practice, so he cannot correctly voice out his thoughts, and he hesitates to speak English every time he is called to participate. He also said that he is embarrassed because of mispronounced words. Sometimes, he is also shy whenever many people are listening to him. Nevertheless, the coping mechanisms of P1 are the following, he prepares himself whenever there will be oral recitation activity, chooses to study ahead of time and read the materials repeatedly. He also listens to his teacher's Feedback and learns from their comments and suggestions. Moreover, he tried to practice speaking in English and read more about English materials.

The Case of P2

P2 is a third-year, section 1 college student. He is 29 years old and can speak four languages, particularly Tagalog Cebuano, English, and Bla'an. His first language is Bla'an. Based on the result, P2 fears committing mistakes in either speaking or writing English, she also finds it challenging to pronounce unfamiliar words correctly, and she gets embarrassed whenever his classmates laugh at him during English reporting. For him, students are having problems in their speaking because of poor grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation. He also admits that he knows how to communicate using English, but he needs to be fluent.

Meanwhile, P2 could cope with his difficulties in speaking English by practicing it during his free time; P2 also read books, watched English movies, and used the language inside the classroom.

The Case of P3

P3 is a third-year, section 1 college student. She is 27 years old and can speak languages – English, Tagalog, and Maranao. She is a Muslim, and her first language is Maranao. Based on the result, P3 has confusion with English grammar. Thus, it makes him hard to communicate with people using the said language. He also admits that he has difficulties pronouncing English words. He also has a problem constructing English sentences because of his poor vocabulary. He is also too shy to get criticized by other people whenever he speaks English. On the other hand, the case of P3 shows that he copes with his difficulties by trying his best to interact with his teacher using the English language, he also makes English reading a habit, and he reads books and listens to audiobooks about different English stories. Additionally, he builds his confidence in speaking English through oral recitation, reporting, and demonstration.

The Case of P4

P4 is a third-year, section 2 college student. He is 21 years old and can speak three languages: Tagalog, Cebuano, and English. His first language is Cebuano. Based on the results, one of the reasons why he sometimes hesitates to speak is that he is afraid to be judged by his peers. P4 also said that he fears committing mistakes, especially when he commits grammatical errors and answers incorrectly. The case of P4 shows that he frequently mispronounces words because he has a fake tooth, which makes it hard for him to pronounce words, precisely words with "sh" sounds.

Despite all those difficulties in speaking English, P4 was able to cope with his problem through the help of his teacher; he listens to the advice of his teacher and works with his weaknesses. He also studies English, watches movies to expound his vocabulary, and practices building self-confidence.

The Case of P5

P5 is also a third-year, section 2 college student. He is 21 years old and can speak four languages. Those are Cebuano, Tausug, Tagalog, and English. She is a Muslim, and her first language is Tausug. Based on the result, the case of P5 is that he hesitates to speak in front of people because of his speaking difficulties; he also feels shy whenever he mispronounces words. He mentioned that he is not good enough with his vocabulary and loses his confidence and motivation when he speaks English with incorrect grammar.

Meanwhile, his coping mechanisms are the following: he converses with his friends using the English language because he wants to improve or enhance his speaking skills. He also read books to learn new words and expound his vocabulary. P5 also uses cognitive strategy to overcome his fear of speaking, and he takes notes if someone is talking in English.

The Case of P6

P6 is a third-year, section 3 college student. She is 23 years old and can speak two languages, English and Cebuano. His first language is Cebuano. Based on the result, P6 has negative experiences with speaking in English. She said that sometimes he mispronounces words because his tongue is too small, then when she mispronounces a word, she gets shy. In addition, she has speaking difficulty whenever he participates in oral recitation or spontaneous and extemporaneous speech because he consistently mispronounces English words. Thus, she feels unmotivated. Nevertheless, P7 was able to cope with her speaking difficulties by listening to the Feedback of her teachers and applying their advice in real-life situations. She also evaluates her level of speaking difficulties.

The Case of P7

P7 is a third-year college, section 3 student. She is 21 years old and can speak three languages. Those are Cebuano, Tagalog, and English. Based on the result, P7 always gets tense whenever she speaks in English; she also said that she sometimes fails to deliver the correct words she wants to utter. Moreover, she admits that she has a problem with fluency. However, P7 was able to cope with her speaking difficulties. She uses cognitive strategy to overcome her fear, and she practices guessing meaning from context and using imagery for memorization. She also listens to her teachers' Feedback because she believes they can help her learn English.

Implication for Practice

The study's key results may help the school of GenSantos Foundation College, Incorporated, design a springboard to address the concern of English-major students concerning their experiences with speaking difficulties by providing a speech laboratory to practice their speaking skills. Also, teachers may be able to develop and choose appropriate teaching-learning techniques, approaches, and methods like an English-only policy to build the confidence of the students; in addition, teachers may also join an English Communication Training Program to improve their communications skills, gain expert knowledge, network with others, and enhance their English language skills so that they can also train English significant students to become an effective communicator.

Additionally, this study may help the parents become aware of the speaking difficulties faced by the students and will be mindful of the coping mechanisms to address the students' concerns. Meanwhile, the English-major students may be able to overcome their fears and follow the coping mechanisms, strategies, and techniques found based on the result of this research; they may also join pieces of training and seminars related to improving language communication skills in English to build their self-confidence and productivity when speaking English, practice professional communication technique, achieve greater comprehension for how language works which may increase literacy in enhancing English speaking difficulties.

Also, this study may help future researchers to learn and understand important information about the speaking difficulties of English-major students and the effective strategies to cope with them. Future researchers may also use this study as a springboard whenever they want to conduct related research about exploring English-major students' speaking difficulties.

Moreover, another implication for practice is presented based on the themes of the study.

Lack of Speaking Practice. Lack of speaking practice is one of the participants' difficulties in speaking English; thus, it is recommended for them to practice speaking English, like learning from native speakers, listening to educational videos about speaking English, and speaking English regularly.

Lack of General Knowledge. Some participants also concluded that they need more general knowledge of English. Thus, it is recommended that they may study the rules of subject-verb agreement or equip themselves with learning about other grammar rules.

Fear of Mistakes. The participants fear committing mistakes whenever they speak English; to avoid this, they may spend their time studying English and listening to informative videos about how to speak correct English words. Also, they are recommended to speak to their friends using the English language to boost their self-esteem in speaking English.

Unfamiliar Word Pronunciation. Based on the participants' responses, most concluded that they struggle with unfamiliar word pronunciation. Those not used to speaking English are more likely to have difficulty acquiring intelligible pronunciation, with the difficulty increasing markedly. Thus, the participants are recommended to practice better vocabulary, leading them to pronounce words correctly.

Low Motivation. The participants feel that they need more confidence whenever they speak English. They have low motivation; they feel demotivated every time they speak English in front of many people; thus, to boost their confidence, they must engage in activities related to speech delivery; also, they need to be exposed to events that enhance speaking skills.

Being Ready. It is recommended that the participants always be prepared and ready, especially if there are activities like oral recitation since it is essential so that they will not cram in the actual presentation.

Accepting Feedback. Participants should be willing to accept their English teachers' Feedback. That Feedback is helpful for their growth in learning more about the English language. Also, Feedback will help them improve their English-speaking skills. They must learn that there is always room for improvement, and practice helps them improve.

Practicing English. The participants found that keeping their English skills sharp was an effective means of managing their stress. They improve their command of the English language by engaging in conversation with their peers and other people. Conversing in the target language can significantly improve their English speaking abilities. They concluded that increasing their time learning English helped them overcome the challenges of speaking English. With this being said, it is recommended that they continue to practice English at home and, most significantly, in school.

Building Self-Confidence. The participants should continue to overcome the challenges of speaking English by boosting their self-confidence through activities such as reading books, watching movies, conversing with others whose first language is English, participating in public speaking, and overcoming their fears. They acknowledge that developing their sense of self-worth will never be easy for them, but they are optimistic that they will succeed thanks to their dogged drive, which will allow them to excel in the use of English in the years to come.

Implication for Future Research

For future researchers conducting research similar to the present investigation, the data and information gathered in this research can serve as their baseline information in conducting a study about English speaking difficulties. The findings and information in this study can add to the existing body of knowledge.

Additionally, this study may serve as an avenue for future researchers to look for more effective coping mechanisms to enhance students' English knowledge, poor vocabulary, lack of confidence and motivation, and other speaking difficulties. This study will also deepen future researchers' perspectives on major English students' experiences regarding their speaking difficulties and coping mechanisms.

Concluding Remarks

This study reveals the case phenomenon of the English language difficulties of the Bachelor of Secondary Education major in GenSantos Foundation College, Incorporated English students. Based on the findings, the participants can overcome their English Language difficulties by implementing appropriate strategies. The factors that caused their difficulties, as manifested by emotional tension, physiological effects, and mental difficulties while they speak English, were due to lack of speaking practice, word usage, fear of mistakes, low motivation, and lack of general knowledge of English speaking. However, exercising their initiative through helpful tools, putting their thoughts into writing, practicing, reading books,

seeking help watching English movies, overcoming their low confidence level, and requesting constructive Feedback enable them to cope with their English language speaking difficulties. This initiative and their open-mindedness have lessened their anxiety and increased their confidence in developing their skills in learning and speaking English.

As a researcher, I realized that the participants' experiences concerning their speaking difficulties are not accessible. However, the great thing is that they can overcome their difficulties by employing some coping mechanisms which strengthen and help them become better at learning the English language. This case study leaves a unique viewpoint that helps me to appreciate the English-major students significantly and value the essence of research.

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